

Design and Fabrication of Footpath Cleaning Machine

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ABSTRACT

Our study shows that dirt besides the road causes uncleanness and accident problems. We had developed a semiautomatic road side cleaning machine that insures that dust and dirt in sides of road should be clean. Our design proposes and successfully implemented the use of scrubber and brush that will remove the dust and collect it in to the storage box in which the scrubber is driven by engine which removes the dust and throws it into the path of brush. This brush is driven by speed amplification mechanism which consists of chain and gear drive separately. The motion of brush allows to push the removed dust into the storage box.

Keywords: Vacuum pump, Motor, Storage box

1. INTRODUCTION.

Environment is a place where humans as well as plants and animals live. Keeping it clean and neat is our responsibility. It is necessary to keep our environment clean because we get fresh air, reduce pollution etc. An unclean environment leads to a bad condition of a society, arrival of diseases and many more. In recent years cleanliness is becoming an important factor for the betterment of the nation and so, to support the cause we have conducted a study, prepared a design and working of a Semiautomatic footpath Cleaning Machine. The cleaning machine is an approach to deliver easy and time efficient cleaning of roads, by reducing human efforts.

There are in numerous functions of the Footpath cleaning machine mainly cleanliness is becoming an important factor for the betterment of the nation and so, to support the cause we have conducted Study, prepared a design and working of a Semiautomatic Cleaning Machine. The cleaning machine is an approach to deliver easy and time efficient cleaning of Footpath, by reducing human efforts.

Now, workers are hired to do this stuff but it is impossible to work continuously for workers. So this is time consuming and also costly process because of workers salary. The important factor is eliminating traffic problem because of less manpower as well as accident

1.1 Present Process

The present method of cleaning dust beside road is manual process. In manual process, the road cleaning is done with the help of broom to clean off dirt and dust. A person continuously does a swiping action by a broom in the hand and other person carry trolley which collect the dust and dirt as shown in figure below. If we observing this process, then we could find the following limitations which are given below:

Figure 1: Manual Process

1. This process renders fatigue to the hand and even it cause damage to the shoulder.
2. As it is a continuous process, it produces mental fatigue and hazardous to the health of sweeper.
3. It is time consuming, and laborious process so, no one wants to do it.

1.2 Effect of Dust on Road

1. The dust particles present on the road, when mixes with the fog and forms smog, this decreases the visibility on the road, which results in mishandling and fatal accidents.
2. The contact between the road surface and the surface of tyre reduces due to the presence of dust particle layer between them, during the braking and turning of the vehicle, it causes the problem like skidding.
3. Foreign dust particles when entering in the eyes of the driver or the rider causes discomfort and Irritation which is a critical problem when driving or riding on a busy road.

2. METHODOLOGY

Fabrication of Road Cleaner is a device used clean the roads, floor, corridors, etc. at places like railway station, bus stop, highways, with less stress and more efficiency towards human effort. This project is having more scope towards cleanliness (swachh bharath) and keeping areas more sanitizing.

In this our project fabrication of road cleaner is eco-friendly, low main maintenance low cost, easy mechanism & were mainly concentrated about the large area which should be clean & sanitized. In this our machine can be 90% efficiency to the energy applied by us can be well efficiency to the energy used by simple gear & chain drives. Firstly we have decided to make vacuum cleaner controlled by remote control and we have done with model. After that we have faced many issues with like succession power & dust collecting area, so we have now done with the road cleaner which doesn't require any electricity & like that problem & when we start & went with the idea, firstly we have decided to ready with the frame & brush, so we Pavan Reddy and Nithin went for brush purchasing and Rohith, Manu, Prajwal, ShanthKumar was went for frame fabrication.

Now we are set with the frame and brush, then we bought the wheels and tires from scrap at the yelachenahalli, then we are successful to fit with the frame and wheels. After that we have challenging situation to place the gears and the brush and bushes for the brush . so we took some assistance from babu(friend) as he have experience in working in the fabrication shop from many years and he is close to rohith and from his help we carefully placed that gears (meshing) in their place by the arc welding , after we have fixed a shaft for the brush .

3. MAIN COMPONENTS

3.1 Frame

It is main component of the machine which support and carry all parts like Motor, Vacuum dust collector, battery etc. the frame is made of mild steel and CAD model of frame is shown below.

Figure: Frame

A vacuum pump is a device that draws gas molecules from a sealed volume in order to leave behind a partial vacuum. The job of a vacuum pump is to generate a relative vacuum within a capacity. The first vacuum pump was invented in 1650 by Otto von Guericke, and was preceded by the suction pump, which dates to antiquity.

3.2 DC Motor

Motor is the prime mover of the driving mechanism through which the scrubber is rotated and cleans dust beside the road. For efficient scrubbing of dust from the road, we selected a 24V Geared DC motor having 97.8N-cm Rated Torque. This motor is operated by a battery.

Specifications Manufacturer- In-horse DC Motor,

Model- MTP-P25-1JK40 1/6 HP (0.166) 12V 1732 rpm 7.5 Vacuum

Specification Dimensions – (415*415*440)mm Weight – (6 kg) Suction of motor
– 2000 mm/wc (19600 pa)

Blower efficiency- 30 lit/sec Noise- less than 88 dB Power-1200w Voltage-230v,

Figure: Dc Motor

3.3 Scrubber Brush

The scrubber brush is another main component of our machine which is directly connected with the motor through the spindle shaft and rotated at motor speed. The scrubber brush provides the sweeping action which cleans dust beside the road divider.

Figure: Scrubber Brush

3.4 Collecting box

Sheet metal is metal formed by an industrial process into thin, flat pieces. Sheet metal is one of the fundamental forms used in metalworking and it can be cut and bent into a variety of shapes. Countless everyday objects are fabricated from sheet metal. Thicknesses can vary significantly; extremely thin sheets are considered foil or leaf, and pieces thicker than 6 mm (0.25 in) are considered plate.

Sheet metal is available in flat pieces or coiled strips. The coils are formed by running a continuous sheet of metal through a roll slitter. In most of the world, sheet metal thickness is consistently specified in millimeters. In the US, the thickness of sheet metal is commonly specified by a traditional, non-linear measure known as its gauge. The larger the gauge number, the thinner the metal. Commonly used steel sheet metal ranges from 30 gauge to about 7 gauge. Gauge differs between ferrous (iron based) metals and nonferrous metals such as aluminum or copper; copper thickness, for example is measured in ounces, which represents the weight of copper contained in an area of one square foot. Parts manufactured from sheet metal must maintain a uniform thickness for ideal results

There are many different metals that can be made into sheet metal, such as aluminum, brass, copper, steel, tin, nickel and titanium. For decorative uses, some important sheet metals include silver, gold, and platinum (platinum sheet metal is also utilized as a catalyst).

Figure: Dust Collecting Box

3.5 Brush

Figure: Brush

Nylon filled cylinder brushes are commonly used in many applications for scrubbing, dusting, and cleaning conveyed objects or conveyor belts. Some common applications include bakery and food conveyors, plating processes, lumber mills, block and brick manufacturing, and other conveyor cleaning applications. Cylindrical nylon brushes offer the following characteristics in most applications: excellent fatigue life, good abrasion resistance, low to moderate absorption of water (3% to 9%), an excellent bend recovery rate, resistance to most common solvents, and suitability for use in weak acids.

Nylon 6-12 is approved for use in cylinder brush applications with direct food-contact, while Nylon 6.6 is a medium grade of filament suitable for most dry industrial applications. Spiral Brushes Inc. uses nylon 6.6 as our regular duty filament for most industrial cylinder brush applications. Compared to nylon 6.12, nylon 6.6 has a higher moisture absorption rate at 9%. It therefore loses approximately half its stiffness when exposed to wet environments. Nylon 6.6 also has limited resistance to many common chemicals.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From this projects we conclude that, our machine is safe ,eco-friendly and reduce the cost and time of dust cleaning done by manual process .This is the best alternative method for cleaning road side dust.

In our cleaning machine when motor starts, scrubber brush scrubs the dust separated on road divider and cyclone vacuum collector collect that dust in to the collector tank .Only one person is required to operate machine and cleaning is done at very less human effort.

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